

THE NEED FOR THE INNOVATIVE EMPLOYEES IN INNOVATION EPOCH

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Etmishboev Shakhzodbek

Student of the Fergana branch of the TATU

Tolibjonov KHurshidbek

Student of Kokand University

Azamov Shoxruxmirzo

*Student of the Fergana branch of
the TATU*

Abstract: *The following article introduces innovative employees as an asset to companies and analyses the ways how to create innovativeness among them. The study not only illustrates the economic importance of innovative employees, but also shows that the right managers are much more important motivators than working environments, incentives or salaries.*

Key words: *digitalization, innovation, creativity, competition, companies, motivation.*

In the current age of digitalization and globalization, having creativity and innovativeness as a critical attribute in employees is becoming a mainstream demand for service and hospitality organizations. The hospitality industry in the 21st century is rapidly changing. Customers' demands are changing, and so is their involvement in the value creation process of the firm. With these changes comes an alarming rate of economic and exponentially fierce competition, which requires innovation as a cornerstone for organizational sustainability. Innovation means renewal - a renewal that is successfully launched on the market. Innovations are important for start-ups to set foot in the market, but even large companies need innovations in order not to be overtaken by smaller ones. But why are some companies more innovative than others and what role does employee motivation play here?

The most important factor for a company's ability to innovate is the motivation and commitment of its employees. Innovative employees secure a sustainable market advantage, bring money and thus contribute considerably to the survival of a company. The innovation culture of a company is directly related to the commitment of managers and employees. In companies with a high level of employee commitment, managers focus more on people-related management tasks such as

coaching, feedback and employee motivation. In companies with a high level of commitment, all managers see themselves as coaches for their employees; in companies with a low level of commitment, this only applies to 34 percent. Companies with a high level of commitment achieve a higher degree of fulfillment, especially with regard to respectful handling, making sense and recognition. While 95 percent of managers in highly committed companies confirm that employees understand the meaning of their work and know their value contribution to the company, this is only true for 48 percent of those with low commitment. A respectful relationship between superiors and employees is 100 percent in companies with high commitment, but only 52 percent in those with low commitment. A company needs employees who show entrepreneurship within the company - people who have the mindset of a startup founder but work for a company. Corporate entrepreneurs are an extreme example of innovation culture, but even small gestures on the part of the manager bring the innovation culture in the right direction: Many innovations of employees with high innovation potential fail because their superiors ignore new ideas - or simply do not listen. From their daily practice, however, employees usually know best about their area of responsibility and are most likely to recognize the opportunities for improvement. It is therefore all the more important to listen to employees accordingly - these are important impulses for motivation and employee satisfaction.

To motivate employees, the exchange of information is just as important as the advisory function of management. If managers provide their employees with the necessary knowledge, this also strengthens motivation.

Some managers do not take their employees' ideas and suggestions seriously, which ultimately represents a significant obstacle to a lively innovation culture. In some cases this conceals the jealousy of the superior towards the employee, who brings out an innovative idea. Jealousy is in principle a killer of innovation culture and thus a major barrier to establishing a positive innovation culture. Increasing responsibility for tasks influences employee satisfaction, motivation and creativity. Employees with higher responsibilities are happier and more committed than those who have to do irresponsible or unimportant jobs.

To motivate employees to be innovative, good communication and a clear flow of information between management and employees are necessary. Insufficient information flow and poor cooperation between different departments have just as negative an impact on the company as a bad image or management. In addition, valuable ideas are often not

pursued and abandoned due to a lack of communication. Many employees have good ideas, but quickly reject them because they are not aware of the value of their ideas or because their ideas are not valued. Management often makes the mistake of saying that new ideas are too expensive - according to the motto "We certainly won't! Moreover, when new ideas arise, there is often a lack of feedback from the manager. The same applies to praise and appreciation for the fact that the employee has taken the trouble to work out and propose a new idea. However, recognizing and appreciating employee ideas accordingly is an important motivational aspect and should be anchored accordingly in the innovation culture. Sustained innovation comes from developing a collective sense of purpose; from unleashing the creativity of people throughout your organization and from teaching them how to recognize unconventional opportunities. Here are seven strategies for sustaining innovation in your organization.

The need for constant reinvention is a given in today's business environment. And while a breakthrough product or concept can catapult an organization ahead of its competitors, in these fast-paced times, that advantage is often short-lived.

While major product or service breakthroughs make headlines, it's the steady incremental innovations made by employees every day that give an organization the sustained growth it needs. Sustained innovation comes from developing a collective sense of purpose; from unleashing the creativity of people throughout your organization and from teaching them how to recognize unconventional opportunities.

As innovative ideas surface, a clear sense of mission empowers front-line employees to act on new ideas that further your company's purpose.

Leaders create the psychological environment that fosters sustained innovation at all levels. The challenge is that as an organization grows, management structures and bureaucracies, designed to channel growth, tend to create barriers to small-scale enhancements. While there are exceptions, in larger organizations employees tend to feel removed from the function of innovation and are less likely to take independent action or offer revolutionary ideas. The commitment to establishing the right psychological conditions for innovation needs to start at the top. This means that, as a leader, you need to consider your own assumptions about innovation and their role in creating and changing your organization's culture. You need to appreciate the value of incremental as well as major innovations, understand the psychology of innovation and take the lead in promoting an

innovative culture. Otherwise, it's just not going to happen. While your organization's innovative capability depends on multiple factors, there are several steps you can take to create the psychological conditions that favor inventive thinking, regardless of your industry or the size of your organization.

An essential success factor for every innovation is the innovation culture in a company. Managers play the key role here. If they see themselves as coaches, transfer decision-making authority, give regular feedback and value the ideas of their employees, the motivation of the employees and thus also the innovative ability of the company increases significantly. Please also read our article "10 Measures to create a culture of innovation".

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